

The Cladisticules

Anatomy of a Cladisticule

	Head fused to thorax: (0) yes; (1) no.	Toes: (0) two; (1) one.	Legs: (0) four; (1) six.	Antennae: (0) absent; (1) present.	Horns: absent (0); present (1).	Thorax: (0) no pattern; (1) hour glass	Abdomen: (0) white; (1) black.
Joe*							
April							
Mike							
Tanya							
Bobby							
Jason							
Jerry							
Jane							